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RADON GAS AND ITS EFFECT ON HUMAN HEALTH

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Annotation: In the course of the study, the features of radon gas and its effect on human health were studied. The properties of radon gas, the ways of entering the human body, the effect on organs and tissues of the human body, methods of preventing radon from entering the human body and preventing radon-dependent diseases are described in detail.

Keywords: radon, human health, penetration routes, prevention

Introduction.

Radon gas is one of the most common radioactive gases in the natural environment. It is a product of the decay of radioactive elements, such as uranium and thorium, in soil, rocks and water. Radon is unpleasantly known for its potentially dangerous effects on human health. In this article we will look at its properties, ways of getting into the body and its effect on health [1-8].

Properties of radon gas.

Radon gas is colorless and odorless. It is an inert gas, which means that it does not react with other chemical elements. It is this property that makes radon difficult to detect and highlights its potential danger. Radon is an alpha emitter that emits alpha particles, which have a low penetration depth into the human body, but can cause harm if the source of radon is nearby.

Ways of getting into the body.

The main way radon enters the human body is inhalation. Radon is released from the soil and rocks and can penetrate into our living

environment through cracks and flaws in building materials. Indoors, radon can accumulate and reach a dangerous concentration level. In addition, a small amount of radon can enter the body through food and drinking water, but the contribution of this pathway is insignificant compared to inhalation.

The effect of radon gas on the human body.

Constant inhalation of radon can lead to an increased risk of developing radon cancer, the most significant radiation-related disease. The main organ sensitive to radon is the lungs. When radon is inhaled, it can linger in the lungs for a long time and emit alpha particles that cause damage to cells, which can eventually lead to the development of cancerous tumors.

The symptoms of radon cancer are usually implicit and can manifest after a long time. However, they include persistent cough, frequent respiratory infections, difficulty breathing, chest pain and hemoptysis. If radon cancer is not treated in time, it can progress to an incurable condition.

Prevention and precautions.

Since radon gas is invisible and odorless, its detection requires special tools and precautions. However, there are several steps that can be taken to reduce the risk of exposure to radon.

It is important to regularly assess the level of radon in the home environment. This can be done using the radon test, which are offered in most countries. If the radon level exceeds the recommended standards, it is necessary to take measures to reduce it. For example, it is possible to improve ventilation in the room or install a radon removal system. You should also limit the time spent in protracted rooms, especially in basements and basement floors.

Conclusion.

Radon gas is a dangerous radioactive gas that can harm human health. Inhaling radon can lead to the development of radon cancer, which can be fatal. Conducting regular indoor radon level checks and taking precautions can reduce the risk of radon exposure to health. The safety of our homes and places of stay is an important aspect of our public concern, and the fight against radon is no exception.

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